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Importin 8 is activated in childhood brain cancer.

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We clustered a group of childhood brain cancers together when identifying the most significant transcriptional changes in brain tumors that affect children to discover common transcriptional changes despite disparate etiologies. We identified activation of a nuclear import receptor (Importin 8), molecules that functions in transport of cargos between the cytoplasm and nucleus, as a common transcriptional perturbation in childhood brain cancer.

1 **Results**

2 We measured total transcription in a collection of childhood brain tumors, including tumors of the ATRT,
3 pilocytic astrocytoma, glioblastoma, medulloblastoma, adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma,
4 ependymoma, ependymoma (supratentorial ZFTA-RELA fusion), ganglioma, and diffuse midline glioma.

5 GSE243682

6 *n*=5 normal brain

7 *n*=124 childhood brain tumors

8
9 We identified the nuclear import receptor importin 9 (*IPO9*) as a differentially expressed gene and
10 common therapeutic vulnerability in childhood brain tumors. *IPO9* was differentially expressed greater
11 than 96% of the brain transcriptome.

12

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FC</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
55705	2.95e-04	0.206	-3.6197291	-0.7441942	4163.565	IPO9	849/27159	96.9

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15 **Discussion**

16 We identified here the nuclear importin receptor importin 9 as transcriptionally activated in childhood brain
17 tumors.
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Methods

We measured total transcription in childhood brain tumors using publicly available or published data and R-based computational methods.